

The orientation between two planets in outer space

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We view two planets with the masses m_1, m_2 in R^2 . m_1 shall be in the origin. The position of m_2 shall be at $(r, 0)$. With that both planets have the distance r . One observer is stationed at position $p = (x, y)$ (see figure):

The accelerations caused by the gravitation of both planets are:

$$b_1 = \frac{Gm_1}{x^2 + y^2} \quad b_2 = \frac{Gm_2}{(r-x)^2 + y^2}$$

G is the gravitational constant. Now we look at the following figure:

Now the angles $\beta_1 = \angle(\vec{b}_r, \vec{b}_1)$ and $\beta_2 = \angle(\vec{b}_r, \vec{b}_2)$ are interesting. $\vec{b}_r = \vec{b}_1 + \vec{b}_2$ is the resultant acceleration. With the first figure we can conclude:

$$\alpha = \arctan\left(\frac{x}{y}\right) + \arctan\left(\frac{r-x}{y}\right)$$

With $\cos(180^\circ - \alpha) = -\cos \alpha$ and the cosine law we obtain:

$$b_r^2 = b_1^2 + b_2^2 + 2b_1b_2 \cos \alpha$$

With the cosine law we get the relations:

$$b_2^2 = b_1^2 + b_r^2 - 2b_1b_r \cos \beta_1 \quad b_1^2 = b_2^2 + b_r^2 - 2b_2b_r \cos \beta_2$$

We solve to $\cos \beta_1$ respectively $\cos \beta_2$ and then we insert the equation of b_r :

$$\cos \beta_1 = \frac{b_1^2 + b_r^2 - b_2^2}{2b_1b_r} = \frac{b_1 + b_2 \cos \alpha}{\sqrt{b_1^2 + b_2^2 + 2b_1b_2 \cos \alpha}}$$

$$\cos \beta_2 = \frac{b_2^2 + b_r^2 - b_1^2}{2b_2b_r} = \frac{b_2 + b_1 \cos \alpha}{\sqrt{b_1^2 + b_2^2 + 2b_1b_2 \cos \alpha}}$$

Now we have found representations of the angles β_1 and β_2 . $\vec{b}_r$ is the visual vertical.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Theory of orientation - The visual vertical" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag, Berlin, 2002